

Supplemental Material

Sex differences in glucose-regulating neurohormonal pathways – potential impact for type 2 diabetes development

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S1. Eligibility criteria for the main study

Inclusion criteria

- Males and females aged 18-70 years
- BMI 18.5-50 kg/m²
- No diabetes or diagnosis of type 2 diabetes (according to WHO criteria) with less than 8 years duration. Acceptable glycemic control last three months with HbA1c 45-65 mmol/mol for subjects on sulfonylurea or DPP4-inhibitors, otherwise 45-70 mmol/mol. Fasting glucose 5.0 -10.0 mmol/l on the day of the experiments.

Exclusion criteria

1. History or sign of any clinically significant disease or disorder which, in the opinion of the investigator, may either put the subject at risk because of participation in the study, or influence the results or the subject's ability to participate in the study.
2. Established cardiovascular disease (ischemic heart disease, heart failure, stroke, peripheral arterial disease).
3. Microvascular complications (eGFR<30, more than moderate diabetes retinopathy; diabetic foot ulcers or history of amputation).
4. No glucose-lowering drug or, for participants with type 2 diabetes, any antidiabetic drug other than metformin, repaglinide, sulfonylurea (glimepiride, glipizide and glibenclamide) or DPP4-inhibitors (sitagliptin, linagliptin, vildagliptin and saxagliptin) or more than 2 antidiabetic drugs in combination.
5. Use of anabolic steroids, systemic treatment with glucocorticoids, beta blockers, antipsychotic drugs or other drugs deemed to potentially interfere with the results, as assessed by physician.
6. Pregnant or planning to be pregnant during the study.
7. Known or suspected history of significant drug abuse.
8. History of alcohol abuse or excessive intake of alcohol as judged by investigator.
9. History of severe allergy/hypersensitivity or ongoing allergy/hypersensitivity, as judged by the investigator.
10. Judgment by the investigator that the subject should not participate in the study if considers subject unlikely to comply with study procedures, restrictions and requirements.

S2. Statistical method details

Missingness

To allow for calculation of AUC, missing data in the beginning or at the end of the respective interval were imputed as last observation carried forward or next observation carried backward, as deemed appropriate.

Glucagon samples had not been obtained for 3 men. Catecholamines had not been obtained for 13/6/6 (men/post-/premenopausal women) in the hypoglycemic clamp and 13/6/5 (men/post-/premenopausal women) in the hyperglycemic clamp. HRV data was incomplete and thus excluded from the analysis for 5/3/2 (men/post-/premenopausal women) in the hypoglycemic clamp men/pre-/postmenopausal women) and 5/3/1 (men/post-/premenopausal women) in the hyperglycemic clamp. These missing neurohormonal assessments were not imputed.

M-value was missing for one woman who did not complete the hypoglycemic clamp. To allow for comparison of different models, M-value was imputed as the mean M-value among women for this individual. Otherwise, missing data were handled as such and was not imputed.

Assessment of model fit and linear regression assumptions

Model fit and fulfilment of linear regression assumptions were evaluated visually with the performance package (v. 0.12.4, Lüdtke, 2021) and if necessary, dependent variables were transformed, for example to the natural logarithm. The model fit of more parametrized models was evaluated based on the p-value of the likelihood ratio test in comparison with the smaller model, $p < 0.05$ indicating a significant improvement as a result of adding more parameters. Influential observations were excluded exploratively but this did not change the results.

Variable selection: models investigating the impact of sex versus other clinical variables on neurohormonal responses

Models were only generated for responses with significant group difference. The impact of main sex hormones (testosterone, estradiol, FSH, LH) was investigated in separate models. In models adjusting for metabolic variables, waist-hip ratio, HbA1c and M-value were selected as independent variables, due to particularly strong associations with neurohormonal responses as shown presently and in previous publications by our research group [1-4]. These variables also reflect different aspect of metabolic dysregulation, namely abdominal obesity, dysglycemia and insulin resistance, respectively. The interaction between sex and type 2 diabetes status as well as the impact of glycemic control (HbA1c) in relation to counter-regulatory hormones was investigated in a separate model.

Variable selection: models investigating the impact of menopausal status and sex hormones versus other clinical variables on neurohormonal responses within each sex

Models were only generated for responses with significant group difference or Spearman correlations with regard to main sex hormones (testosterone, estradiol, FSH, LH). Due to the low sample size and to avoid overfitting, only two independent variables were allowed in the same model. For each response, the metabolic variable (age, BMI, WHR, body fat percentage, fasting glucose, HbA1c, HOMA-IR, M-value) with the strongest Spearman correlation was chosen to adjust for the impact of metabolic status.

Sensitivity analyses

To evaluate differential impact of sex in individuals with and without T2D, as well as to account for differences in glycemic control, a model including sex, T2D, the interaction

between sex and T2D and HbA1c was performed for responses with a significant sex difference. Likewise, menopausal status was adjusted for T2D in one model. Additional models were undertaken to adjust for potential biases resulting from the use of medications for cardiometabolic conditions (metformin, anti-hypertensives, statins) and tobacco use on group differences according to sex and menopausal status.

Linear mixed model details

Glucose was centered to the grand mean and due to the non-linear relationship between neurohormonal assessments and glucose levels, 2nd to 8th degree polynomial terms for the glucose variable were explored and the model with the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) for each dependent variable is presented as the final model. Model estimated marginal means as well as 95% CIs were obtained with the performance package (v. 0.12.4, Lüdtke, 2021) and were plotted along with real data.

S3. Clinical characteristics, tabulated by T2D status

		Men (n=22)	All women (n=28)	Postmenopausal (n=16)	Premenopausal (n=12)
T2D, n (%)		7 (31.8%)	9 (32.1%)	8 (50%)	1 (8.3%)
No T2D, n (%)		15 (68.2%)	19 (67.9%)	8 (50%)	11 (91.5%)
Age, years	T2D	59 (43;62)	55 (50;60)	56 (50;60)	NA
	No T2D	51 (37;57)	44 (32;54)	55 (53;58)	35 (28;43) ^{†††}
BMI, kg/m ²	T2D	29.0 (27.5;39.2)	33.8 (32.6;38.8)	33.7 (32.3;39.3)	NA
	No T2D	28.7 (24.5;33.4)	27.6 (23.4;34.4)	27.7 (23.6;33.6)	27.6 (22.5;43.4)
WHR, ratio	T2D	1.05 (1.03;1.13)	0.96 (0.91;1.01)*	0.94 (0.90;0.99)	NA
	No T2D	0.97 (0.91;1.00)	0.90 (0.83;0.94)**	0.88 (0.84;0.94)	0.90 (0.77;0.96)
Body fat, %	T2D	33.0 (27.5;36.7)	44.4 (40.1;49.9)***	44.6 (41.4;50.8)	NA
	No T2D	23.9 (22.0;30.7)	38.5 (28.7;45.9)**	38.4 (29.7;44.9)	39.8 (25.2;46.4)
Fasting plasma glucose, mmol/l	T2D	8.3 (7.2;10.3)	7.2 (6.4;7.6)*	7.2 (6.5;7.6)	NA
	No T2D	5.8 (5.6;6.1)	5.6 (5.2;6.1)	5.5 (5.1;6.4)	5.7 (5.2;5.9)
IFCC HbA1c, mmol/mol	T2D	58 (50;68)	47 (44;50)*	48 (44;50)	NA
	No T2D	36 (31;37)	35 (32;37)	37 (33;39)	34 (31;36)
Insulin, μ IU/ml	T2D	17.3 (12.6;41.0)	13.0 (11.1;21.7)	16.9 (12.1;22.0)	NA
	No T2D	8.6 (6.1;13.6)	6.9 (5.5;16.4)	7.1 (3.2;15.1)	6.9 (5.7;16.4)
C-peptide, nmol/l	T2D	1.4 (1.0;1.8)	1.3 (1.2;2.0)	1.3 (1.0;1.8)	NA
	No T2D	0.8 (0.6;0.9)	0.7 (0.5;1.2)	0.9 (0.4;1.2)	0.7 (0.5;1.2)
HOMA-IR	T2D	7.1 (4.8;15.0)	4.3 (3.4;6.5)	5.1 (3.8;6.7)	NA
	No T2D	2.4 (1.6;3.6)	1.9 (1.3;4.0)	1.9 (0.7;3.8)	1.9 (1.3;4.6)
^a M-value, mg kgFFM ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	T2D	4.3 (2.7;7.0)	3.8 (2.2;6.5)	4.9 (3.2;6.6)	NA
	No T2D	7.0 (5.1;10.2)	10.3 (8.5;12.1)	11.0 (6.9;15.5)	9.7 (8.8;11.9)
^b Total cholesterol, mmol/l	T2D	4.0 (3.8;4.2)	3.9 (3.4;4.3)	4.0 (3.7;4.4)	NA
	No T2D	4.7 (4.0;5.3)	4.7 (3.7;5.3)	5.1 (4.6;5.4)	3.8 (3.6;4.8)

HDL cholesterol, mmol/l	T2D	1.0 (0.8;1.1)	1.3 (1.1;1.5)*	1.4 (1.0;1.6)	NA
	No T2D	1.1 (0.9;1.4)	1.4 (1.1;1.8)	1.6 (1.1;2.0)	1.2 (1.0;1.4)
LDL cholesterol mmol/l	T2D	2.0 (1.8;2.6)	2.4 (2.2;2.8)	2.1 (1.8;2.6)	NA
	No T2D	3.1 (2.3;3.7)	2.5 (2.2;3.0)	2.6 (2.4;3.4)	2.5 (1.9;2.9)
LDL/HDL, ratio	T2D	2.7 (2.3;2.9)	1.6 (1.2;2.4)*	1.8 (1.2;2.6)	NA
	No T2D	3.3 (1.7;4.0)	1.9 (1.3;2.6)*	1.6 (1.2;2.6)	1.9 (1.5;2.6)
Triglycerides, mmol/l	T2D	1.5 (1.0;2.6)	1.3 (0.9;2.0)	1.4 (1.0;2.2)	NA
	No T2D	1.3 (0.8;1.6)	0.7 (0.5;1.0)*	0.8 (0.5;1.2)	0.7 (0.5;0.8)
Smoking, n (%)	T2D	2 (28.6%)	1 (11.1%)	1 (12.5%)	0 (0%)
	No T2D	1 (6.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Smokeless tobacco, n (%)	T2D	1 (6.7%)	1 (11.1%)	1 (12.5%)	0 (0%)
	No T2D	0 (0%)	1 (5.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (9.1%)
Anti-hypertensives, n (%)	T2D	6 (85.7 %)	2 (22.2 %)*	2 (25.0%)	0 (0%)
	No T2D	0 (0%)	1 (5.3%)	1 (12.5%)	0 (0%)
Statins, n (%)	T2D	6 (85.7 %)	3 (33.3%)	3 (37.5%)	0 (0%)
	No T2D	0	1 (5.3%)	1 (12.5%)	0 (0%)
Metformin, n (%)	T2D	6 (85.7%)	6 (66.7%)	5 (62.5%)	1 (100.0%)
	No T2D	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Diabetes duration, months	T2D	21 (1;37)	17 (12;26)	16 (11;29)	NA
	No T2D	NA	NA	NA	NA

Clinical characteristics. Obtained at the first visit or mean of both visits (fasting glucose, insulin, HOMA-IR). Data presented as median (IQR). T2D, type 2 diabetes; WHR, waist-to-hip ratio; HOMA-IR, homeostatic model for assessment of insulin resistance; FFM, fat free mass; HDL, high density lipoprotein; LDL, low density lipoprotein. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 vs men. †††p<0.001 vs postmenopausal women. Measurements missing for ^a0/1/0 (men/post-/premenopausal women), ^b4/3/1

S4. Sex hormones and neurohormonal assessments at baseline, tabulated by T2D status

		Men (n=22)	All women (n=28)	Postmenopausal (n=16)	Premenopausal (n=12)
T2D, n (%)		7 (31.8%)	9 (32.1%)	8 (50%)	1 (8.3%)
No T2D, n (%)		15 (68.2%)	19 (67.9%)	8 (50%)	11 (91.5%)
Total Testosterone, nmol/l	T2D	9.8 (7.1;12.6)	0.6 (0.3;1.0)***	0.5 (0.3;1.0)	NA
	No T2D	17.2 (12.0;19.9)	0.5 (0.1;1.0)***	0.3 (0.1;0.8)	0.7 (0.3;1.1)
Free Testosterone, nmol/l	T2D	0.24 (0.22;0.26)	0.01 (0.01;0.02)***	0.01 (0.01;0.02)	NA
	No T2D	0.35 (0.29;0.44)	0.01 (0.00;0.02)***	0.00 (0.00;0.02)	0.01 (0.00;0.02)
Total Estradiol, pmol/l	T2D	118 (75;143)	62 (40;234)	61 (30;89)	NA
	No T2D	113 (93;155)	229 (53;658)	54 (27;93)	307 (229;755) ^{††}
Free Estradiol, pmol/l	T2D	3.7 (2.1;4.6)	1.7 (1.0;8.1)	1.6 (0.8;2.8)	NA
	No T2D	3.4 (2.7;3.9)	6.5 (1.3;23.7)	1.3 (0.7;2.3)	11.2 (6.5;27.4) ^{††}
Testosterone:Estradiol, ratio	T2D	85.1 (58.2;158.2)	9.0 (3.1;16.3)***	10.2 (5.4;16.4)	NA
	No T2D	141.9 (117.6;162.4)	2.5 (0.8;5.9)***	4.2 (0.9;18.0)	2.2 (0.5;3.2)
SHBG, nmol/l	T2D	22 (22;39)	28 (18;35)	25 (17;31)	NA
	No T2D	32 (23;45)	44 (29;78)	35 (24;96)	48 (31;71)
FSH, IU/ml	T2D	5.0 (4.4;6.6)	51.0 (21.9;64.0)**	51.5 (38.3;66.0)	NA
	No T2D	3.6 (3.1;6.1)	6.7 (3.9;64.0)	66.5 (46.5;73.5)	3.9 (2.4;6.6) ^{†††}
LH, IU/ml	T2D	3.6 (2.9;3.8)	24.0 (14.1;43.0)***	33.0 (16.2;43.5)	NA
	No T2D	4.7 (3.6;6.1)	8.9 (4.9;32.0)**	32.5 (25.3;38.5)	6.1 (3.9;8.2) ^{†††}
Progesterone, nmol/l	T2D	NA	NA	NA	NA
	No T2D	NA	0.7 (0.3;5.6)	NA	0.7 (0.4;14.4)
Prolactin, mIU/l	T2D	130 (101;166)	176 (147;258)*	173 (144;234)	NA
	No T2D	164 (126;202)	227 (181;344)*	203 (151;287)	276 (199;437)
Androstenedione, nmol/l	T2D	1.1 (0.5;2.2)	1.7 (0.5;2.7)	1.9 (0.7;2.9)	NA
	No T2D	2.1 (0.5;4.0)	1.6 (0.5;3.4)	0.5 (0.5;1.9)	2.0 (1.2;5.5) [†]
DHEA-S, μ mol/l	T2D	4.2 (1.8;5.3)	3.2 (1.4;4.9)	3.3 (1.8;5.2)	NA
	No T2D	3.4 (2.8;5.5)	4.1 (2.2;6.2)	2.3 (0.8;6.3)	4.4 (3.2;6.2)

		Men (n=22)	All women (n=28)	Postmenopausal (n=16)	Premenopausal (n=12)
^a Glucagon, pmol/l	T2D	14.5 (12.5;21.3)	7.2 (5.1;9.8)***	7.4 (5.1;10.6)	NA
	No T2D	11.6 (7.1;12.9)	9.6 (6.1;12.2)	10.0 (7.9;10.8)	9.5 (4.4;13.2)
Cortisol, nmol/l	T2D	253 (228;342)	208 (172;309)	237 (158;319)	NA
	No T2D	234 (168;286)	226 (196;310)	254 (198;322)	222 (162;310)
ACTH, pmol/l	T2D	4.8 (2.1;8.1)	3.4 (0.9;4.2)	3.7 (1.2;4.2)	NA
	No T2D	4.0 (3.0;6.2)	2.4 (2.0;2.9)**	2.6 (2.3;5.2)	2.4 (2.0;2.8)
GH, µg/l	T2D	0.07 (0.03;0.22)	0.31 (0.08;0.34)	0.21 (0.06;0.33)	
	No T2D	0.07 (0.03;0.33)	2.24 (0.26;4.35)***	1.22 (0.25;4.13)	2.45 (0.26;4.35)
IGF-1, µg/l	T2D	127 (123;140)	111 (83;144)	109 (82;142)	NA
	No T2D	152 (124;207)	145 (129;195)	130 (109;149)	180 (138;207) [†]
^b Adrenaline, pg/ml	T2D	16.9 (10.2;0.0)	11.3 (4.5;39.1)	21.4 (6.8;42.9)	NA
	No T2D	27.6 (20.3;32.4)	13.4 (6.7;23.6)*	13.7 (6.4;28.2)	13.0 (5.5;20.2)
^b Noradrenaline, pg/ml	T2D	243.5 (116.3;0.0)	192.6 (140.7;332.6)	196.2 (128.9;384.9)	NA
	No T2D	311.1 (187.5;379.6)	210.4 (168.2;306.7)	212.2 (174.4;319.5)	171.6 (150.7;261.5)
^c Heart rate, bpm	T2D	68 (65;78)	69 (65;76)	72 (66;78)	NA
	No T2D	63 (54;66)	65 (59;70)	64 (57;71)	65 (60;69)
^c HF, ms ² log	T2D	1.8 (1.6;2.5)	2.3 (1.7;2.7)	2.2 (1.6;2.7)	NA
	No T2D	2.6 (2.3;3.0)	2.8 (2.5;3.0)	2.5 (2.1;2.9)	2.9 (2.6;3.2)
^c LF:HF, ratio	T2D	0.6 (-0.1;0.8)	0.1 (0.0;0.2)	0.1 (0.0;0.4)	NA
	No T2D	0.3 (0.0;0.4)	0.1 (0.0;0.3)	0.1 (0.0;0.4)	0.1 (0.0;0.2)
SBP, mmHg	T2D	152 (141;156)	142 (136;153)	142 (134;152)	NA
	No T2D	132 (128;138)	120 (110;128)**	122 (116;130)	112 (108;125)
DBP, mmHg	T2D	93 (88;98)	89 (79;92)	89 (75;92)	NA
	No T2D	83 (80;90)	76 (72;85)*	83 (76;85)	74 (68;82)

Fasting hormone levels and HRV indices at rest. Counter-regulatory hormones and HRV indices are mean from both visits, all other hormones obtained at the hypoglycemic clamp visit. DHEA-S, dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate; HF, power of the high frequency component of HRV; LF:HF, ratio between power of the low and high frequency components of HRV; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 vs men, [†]p<0.05, ^{††}p<0.01, ^{†††}p<0.001 vs postmenopausal women. Measurements missing for ^a3/0/0 (men/post-/premenopausal women), ^b13/6/6, ^c5/3/2.

S5. Reproductive status and cycle phase in women

Postmenopausal women (three hysterectomized, two on hormonal intrauterine device) had a median of 7 years (range 5 months – 30 years) since last menstruation. Among the premenopausal women, two were on hormonal uterine devices and one had undergone endometrial ablation. The nine menstruating women were in the follicular phase (n=6 in the hypoglycemic clamp, n=2 in the hyperglycemic phase) or else the luteal phase.

S6. Cortisol, catecholamines and blood pressure in men vs women

Data shown as geometric mean and standard deviations for men (blue squares) and women (pink triangles). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ for AUC (A) or mean (G-J). SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure.

S7. Model summary of linear mixed models investigating the glucose-dependent effect of sex on counter-regulatory responses

		Glucagon	Cortisol	ACTH	GH	ADR	NOR	HR	HF	LF:HF
Type III Fixed Effects										
Sex	<i>p</i>	0.007 **	0.015 *	0.001 **	<0.001 ***	0.149	0.044 *	0.589	0.973	0.060
Glucose	<i>p</i>	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Sex x Glucose	<i>p</i>	0.286	0.027	0.366	<0.001 ***	0.005 **	0.538	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Fixed Effects										
(Intercept)	<i>β</i>	1.57 ***	5.42 ***	1.21 ***	-0.34	3.42 ***	5.41 ***	67.02 ***	2.43 ***	0.41 ***
	<i>SE</i>	(0.10)	(0.04)	(0.10)	(0.19)	(0.16)	(0.08)	(2.59)	(0.10)	(0.05)
Sex (ref. women)	<i>β</i>	0.46 **	0.16 *	0.51 ***	-0.98 ***	0.36	0.30 *	-1.76	0.01	0.15
	<i>SE</i>	(0.16)	(0.06)	(0.15)	(0.27)	(0.24)	(0.14)	(3.25)	(0.15)	(0.08)
Glucose (1st deg)	<i>β</i>	-25.35 ***	-4.64 ***	-2.58	-6.13	-9.01	-5.98 ***	-318.29	2.52 ***	-0.88 **
	<i>SE</i>	(1.86)	(0.68)	(3.85)	(7.99)	(9.00)	(0.86)	(181.75)	(0.66)	(0.30)
Glucose (2nd deg)	<i>β</i>	2.81	2.03 *	17.25 *	44.50 **	36.79 *	3.63 **	-419.73	-4.93 ***	1.32 ***
	<i>SE</i>	(3.15)	(0.81)	(7.13)	(14.81)	(16.39)	(1.14)	(349.24)	(0.97)	(0.33)
Glucose (3rd deg)	<i>β</i>	-8.47 *	-2.79 **	7.06	30.24	11.81	-3.65 **	-665.65	0.35	-
	<i>SE</i>	(3.78)	(0.87)	(8.78)	(18.25)	(19.79)	(1.15)	(439.96)	(1.07)	-
Glucose (4th deg)	<i>β</i>	-1.10	-	16.04 *	36.31 *	31.29 *	-	-520.46	-2.84 ***	-
	<i>SE</i>	(3.06)	-	(7.30)	(15.17)	(15.87)	-	(379.87)	(0.81)	-
Glucose (5th deg)	<i>β</i>	-7.48 ***	-	3.62	17.08	9.60	-	-404.15	-	-
	<i>SE</i>	(1.82)	-	(4.65)	(9.66)	(9.24)	-	(260.01)	-	-
Glucose (6th deg)	<i>β</i>	-	-	6.39 **	11.69 *	10.49 *	-	-244.13	-	-
	<i>SE</i>	-	-	(2.46)	(5.11)	(4.30)	-	(164.93)	-	-
Glucose (7th deg)	<i>β</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-156.10	-	-
	<i>SE</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	(87.15)	-	-
Glucose (8th deg)	<i>β</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-53.76	-	-

	<i>SE</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	(33.04)	-	-
		Glucagon	Cortisol	ACTH	GH	ADR	NOR	HR	HF	LF:HF
Sex × Glucose	β	1.89	-1.58	-7.31	-33.33 ***	-19.90 *	0.32	301.93	-2.39 **	1.34 **
(1st deg)	<i>SE</i>	(2.08)	(0.91)	(3.97)	(8.25)	(9.17)	(1.24)	(181.92)	(0.80)	(0.43)
Sex × Glucose	β	4.07	1.94	-8.82	-23.29	-19.37	-0.72	453.89	4.04 ***	-1.75 ***
(2nd deg)	<i>SE</i>	(3.28)	(1.00)	(7.19)	(14.93)	(16.47)	(1.40)	(349.32)	(1.06)	(0.44)
Sex × Glucose	β	7.73 *	1.14	-13.31	-44.45 *	-24.27	1.52	652.46	-0.12	-
(3rd deg)	<i>SE</i>	(3.88)	(1.03)	(8.82)	(18.34)	(19.86)	(1.40)	(440.01)	(1.14)	-
Sex × Glucose	β	5.86	-	-11.57	-23.46	-23.04	-	528.69	2.76 **	-
(4th deg)	<i>SE</i>	(3.19)	-	(7.36)	(15.30)	(15.96)	-	(379.94)	(0.91)	-
Sex × Glucose	β	2.25	-	-6.76	-24.54 *	-13.68	-	383.42	-	-
(5th deg)	<i>SE</i>	(2.03)	-	(4.74)	(9.87)	(9.40)	-	(260.12)	-	-
Sex × Glucose	β	-	-	-4.66	-8.10	-8.14	-	254.28	-	-
(6th deg)	<i>SE</i>	-	-	(2.62)	(5.44)	(4.62)	-	(165.10)	-	-
Sex × Glucose	β	-	-	-	-	-	-	144.53	-	-
(7th deg)	<i>SE</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	(87.46)	-	-
Sex × Glucose	β	-	-	-	-	-	-	55.13	-	-
(8th deg)	<i>SE</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	(33.85)	-	-
Random Effects										
σ^2		0.34	0.17	0.39	1.70	0.52	0.14	20.31	0.07	0.03
τ_{00}		0.27 _{id}	0.04 _{id}	0.23 _{id}	0.73 _{id}	0.26 _{id}	0.11 _{id}	72.02 _{id}	0.25 _{id}	0.06 _{id}
ICC		0.44	0.18	0.37	0.30	0.33	0.43	0.78	0.78	0.65
N		47 _{id}	50 _{id}	50 _{id}	50 _{id}	26 _{id}	26 _{id}	44 _{id}	44 _{id}	44 _{id}
Observations		830	888	783	784	436	442	772	773	773
Marginal R2 /		0.535 /	0.199 /	0.340 /	0.447 /	0.626 /	0.240 /	0.127 /	0.055 /	0.070 /
Conditional R2		0.741	0.341	0.586	0.612	0.749	0.570	0.808	0.795	0.670

Results from linear mixed models combining the effect of sex (reference category women) and glucose (mean of coinciding and two preceding measurements) on counter-regulatory responses using pooled data from hypo- and hyperglycemic clamps. Glucose levels have been centered to the grand mean before analysis and all hormones have been transformed to the natural logarithm. Polynomial terms of different degrees

(evaluated systematically as described in methods) have been used for glucose. Random effect was subject id (random intercept model). ADR, adrenaline; NOR, noradrenaline; HR, heart rate; HF, power of the high frequency of HRV; LF: HF, ratio between LF (power of the low frequency of HRV) and HF; Sex x Glucose, interaction between sex and glucose; β , estimate of fixed effect; SE , standard error of fixed effect estimate; σ^2 , residual variance; τ_{00} , variance of intercept; ICC, intra-class correlation coefficient; N, number of subjects. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

S8. EHSS scores

Total EHSS scores (A), and within the autonomic (B), neuroglycopenic (C) and malaise (D) domains. Data are shown as median and IQR for men (blue squares) and women (pink triangles). * $p < 0.05$ for peak scores in men vs women.

S9. Glucose, insulin, C-peptide and glucose infusion rate in pre- vs postmenopausal women.

Glucose (A,B), insulin (C,D), C-peptide (E,F) and glucose infusion rate (GIR, G,H) in the hypoglycemic clamp (left panels) and hyperglycemic clamp (right). Data shown as geometric mean and SD (A-F) or median and IQR (G,H) for premenopausal (n=11 left, n=12 right panels, maroon triangles) and postmenopausal women (n=16 left, n=15 right panels, bluegreen circles). *p<0.05 for mean in pre- vs postmenopausal women Iso, isoglycemic phase; Rec, Recovery phase; FFM, fat free mass.

S10. Counter-regulatory hormones in pre- vs postmenopausal women.

Counter-regulatory hormones during hypoglycemic (left panels) and hyperglycemic (right panels) clamps for premenopausal (n=11 left, n=12 right panels, maroon triangles) and postmenopausal women (n=16 left, n=15 right panels, bluegreen circles). Data displayed as geometric mean and SD. *p<0.05 for AUC in pre- vs postmenopausal women. Iso= Isoglycemic phase, Rec= Recovery phase. GH= growth hormone. Glucagon and catecholamine samples missing as described in Supplement S1.

S11. Heart rate variability and hypoglycemic symptoms in pre- vs postmenopausal women

Heart rate variability and hemodynamic responses during hypoglycemic (left panels) and hyperglycemic (right panels) clamps for premenopausal ($n=11$ left, $n=12$ right panels, maroon triangles) and postmenopausal women ($n=16$ left, $n=15$ right panels, bluegreen circles). Data displayed as median and IQR (panels E,F) or geometric mean and SD (all else). * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$ for mean in pre- vs postmenopausal women. Iso, isoglycemic phase; Rec, Recovery phase; HR, heart rate; HF, power of the high frequency of HRV; LF:HF, ratio between power of the low and the high frequency of HRV; EHSS, Edinburgh Hypoglycemic Symptom Scale. Heart variability measures missing as described in Supplement S1.

S12. Hypoglycemic symptoms in pre- vs postmenopausal women

Total EHSS scores (A), and within the autonomic (B), neuroglycopenic (C) and malaise (D) domains. Data are shown as median and IQR for postmenopausal (bluegreen circles) and women (maroon triangles).

S13. Multilinear regressions investigating the impact of sex versus metabolic parameters on counter-regulatory responses to hypoglycemia

	Gluc _{AUC} ^{a,b}	Gluc _{ΔAUC} ^{b,c}	Cort _{AUC}	ACTH _{AUC} ^a	GH _{ΔAUC}	HR _{ΔMEAN} ^e	HF _{ΔMEAN} ^e	LF:HF _{ΔMEAN} ^e
M1, Sex								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.39**	0.26	0.40**	0.43**	0.37**	-0.34*	0.55***	-0.34*
Model <i>R</i> ²	0.149 [†]	0.068	0.158 [†]	0.189 [†]	0.136 [†]	0.113 [†]	0.298 [†]	0.117 [†]
M2, Sex and Testosterone								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.66*	0.41	0.81**	0.88**	-0.01	-0.70*	0.89**	-0.36
Testosterone, std. β	-0.31	-0.16	-0.46	-0.51	0.43	0.42	-0.40	0.03
Model <i>R</i> ²	0.169 [†]	0.074	0.205 [†]	0.246 [†]	0.177 [†]	0.157 [†]	0.338 [†]	0.117
M3, Sex and Estradiol								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.39*	0.28	0.43**	0.43**	0.44**	-0.37*	0.55***	-0.35*
Estradiol, std. β	-0.00	0.07	0.10	0.00	0.24	-0.12	0.01	-0.02
Model <i>R</i> ²	0.149 [†]	0.072	0.167 [†]	0.189 [†]	0.188 [†]	0.125	0.298 [†]	0.117
M4, Sex and FSH								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.32	0.19	0.31	0.56***	0.38*	-0.41*	0.53**	-0.39*
FSH, std. β	-0.12	-0.13	-0.16	0.23	0.02	-0.14	-0.02	-0.09
Model <i>R</i> ²	0.159 [†]	0.081	0.175 [†]	0.226 [†]	0.136 [†]	0.127	0.298 [†]	0.123
M5, Sex and LH								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.33	0.21	0.34*	0.55**	0.35*	-0.42*	0.50**	-0.37
LH, std. β	-0.11	-0.10	-0.11	0.20	-0.03	-0.15	-0.08	-0.05
Model <i>R</i> ²	0.157 [†]	0.074	0.165 [†]	0.215 [†]	0.137 [†]	0.128	0.302 [†]	0.118
M6, Sex and Metabolic Variables								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.33*	0.20	0.38*	0.22	0.22	-0.21	0.41**	-0.33
HbA1c, std. β	-0.17	-0.31	0.11	-0.06	-0.27	-0.25	0.01	-0.06
WHR, std. β	0.05	0.29	-0.20	0.33*	0.56**	0.04	0.17	-0.01
M-Value, std. β	-0.28	0.07	-0.43*	-0.31*	0.29	0.38*	-0.25	-0.02
Model <i>R</i> ²	0.220 [†]	0.154	0.308 ^{†§}	0.442 ^{†§}	0.307 ^{†§}	0.357 ^{†§}	0.424 [†]	0.120
M7, Sex, T2D status and glycemic control								

	Gluc _{AUC} ^{a,b}	Gluc _{ΔAUC} ^{b,c}	Cort _{AUC}	ACTH _{AUC} ^a	GH _{ΔAUC}	HR _{ΔMEAN} ^e	HF _{ΔMEAN} ^e	LF:HF _{ΔMEAN} ^e
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.45**	0.38*	0.40**	0.39**	0.40**	-0.25	0.50**	-0.34
T2D (ref. no), std. β	0.34	0.44	0.29	0.04	0.00	-0.00	-0.11	-0.09
Sex × T2D, std. β	0.37*	0.40*	0.13	-0.10	-0.00	-0.10	0.23	0.04
HbA1c, std. β	-0.43	-0.72*	-0.07	0.22	-0.15	-0.35	0.22	0.01
Model R ²	0.260 [†]	0.249 ^{†§}	0.226 [†]	0.249 [†]	0.158	0.260 [†]	0.390 [†]	0.125
M8, Sex and BMI								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.39**	0.26	0.40**	0.44***	0.36**	-0.34*	0.55***	-0.34*
BMI, std. β	0.08	-0.06	0.08	0.39**	-0.17	-0.51***	0.28*	-0.04
Model R ²	0.156 [†]	0.072	0.164 [†]	0.337 ^{†§}	0.164 [†]	0.374 ^{†§}	0.376 ^{†§}	0.118
M9, Sex and use of metformin								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.38*	0.27	0.38**	0.42**	0.38**	-0.29	0.52***	-0.34*
Metformin (ref. no), std. β	0.05	-0.08	0.18	0.16	-0.12	-0.26	0.11	-0.01
Model R ²	0.152 [†]	0.075	0.190 [†]	0.214 [†]	0.149 [†]	0.178 [†]	0.310 [†]	0.117
M10, Sex and use of anti-hypertensives								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.36*	0.31*	0.38**	0.41**	0.40**	-0.24	0.49**	-0.35*
Antihypertensives (ref. no), std. β	0.12	-0.18	0.10	0.11	-0.17	-0.36*	0.23	0.03
Model R ²	0.162 [†]	0.100	0.168 [†]	0.200 [†]	0.164 [†]	0.237 ^{†§}	0.346 [†]	0.117
M11, Sex and use of statins								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.38*	0.30*	0.38**	0.43**	0.40**	-0.28	0.52***	-0.34*
Statins (ref. no), std. β	0.05	-0.19	0.08	0.06	-0.21	-0.28	0.12	-0.03
Model R ²	0.152 [†]	0.104	0.164 [†]	0.192 [†]	0.179 [†]	0.187 [†]	0.312 [†]	0.118
M12, Sex and tobacco use								
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.41**	0.29	0.41**	0.47***	0.37**	-0.33	0.55***	-0.38*
Tobacco use (ref. no), std. β	-0.14	-0.14	-0.07	-0.19	-0.03	-0.01	-0.00	0.13
Model R ²	0.168 [†]	0.088	0.163 [†]	0.225 [†]	0.137 [†]	0.113	0.298 [†]	0.132

*p<0.05 for standardized beta coefficient (std. β), [†]model p<0.05, [§]p<0.05 vs Model 1, by likelihood ratio test. Gluc, glucagon; Cort, cortisol; GH, growth hormone; HR, heart rate; HF, power of the high frequency HRV component; LF: HF, ratio between power of the low frequency and HF; WHR, Waist-Hip ratio. ^alogtransformed prior to analysis, ^btransformed to the square root prior to analysis. Measurements missing for ^b3/0/0 (men/post-/premenopausal women), ^d13/6/6, ^e5/3/2.

S14. Multilinear regressions investigating the impact of sex versus metabolic parameters on counter-regulatory responses to hyperglycemia

	ACTH _{AUC} ^a	GH _{AUC} ^b	LF:HF _{MEAN} ^c
M1, Sex			
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.36*	-0.48***	0.42**
Model R^2	0.132 [†]	0.234 [†]	0.175 [†]
M2, Sex (ref. women) and metabolic variables			
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.31	-0.32*	0.43**
HbA1c, std. β	0.21	-0.14	0.45**
WHR, std. β	0.04	-0.19	-0.01
M-Value ^d , std. β	-0.00	0.22	0.19
Model R^2	0.187	0.420 ^{†§}	0.332 ^{†§}
M3, Sex (ref. women), T2D status and glycemic control			
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.28	-0.41**	0.39**
T2D (ref. no T2D), std. β	-0.28	0.05	0.14
Sex \times T2D, std. β	0.08	0.23	-0.06
HbA1c, std. β	0.45	-0.42	0.26
Model R^2	0.227 [†]	0.381 ^{†§}	0.315 [†]
M4, Sex (ref. women) and BMI			
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.36**	-0.48***	0.41**
BMI, std. β	0.27*	-0.36**	-0.12
Model R^2	0.203 ^{†§}	0.365 ^{†§}	0.188 [†]
M5, Sex (ref. women) and use of metformin			
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.36*	-0.47***	0.37*
Metformin (ref. no), std. β	-0.00	-0.18	0.33*
Model R^2	0.132 [†]	0.268 [†]	0.283 ^{†§}
M6, Sex (ref. women) and use of anti-hypertensive medication			
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.36*	-0.45**	0.35*
Antihypertensives (ref. no), std. β	-0.00	-0.14	0.36*
Model R^2	0.132 [†]	0.254 [†]	0.299 ^{†§}
M7, Sex (ref. women) and use of statins			
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.37*	-0.46***	0.37*
Statins (ref. no), std. β	-0.03	-0.14	0.37*
Model R^2	0.133 [†]	0.254 [†]	0.305 ^{†§}
M8, Sex (ref. women) and tobacco use			
Sex (ref. women), std. β	0.37**	-0.48***	0.38*
Tobacco (ref. no), std. β	-0.07	-0.09	0.27
Model R^2	0.137 [†]	0.242 [†]	0.249 [†]

* $p < 0.05$, [†]model $p < 0.05$, [§] $p < 0.05$ vs Model 1, by likelihood ratio test. LF: HF, ratio between power of the low frequency and power of the high frequency; std β , standardized beta coefficient; SE, standard error; fGlucose, fasting glucose; WHR, Waist-Hip ratio. ^atransformed to the square root prior to analysis, ^blogtransformed prior to analysis. Measurements missing for ^c5/3/1 (men/post-/premenopausal women) ^d0/1/0 (imputed to the mean M-value for women).

S15. Glucagon responses during hypoglycemia in men vs women stratified by T2D status

Data shown as median (IQR) for men (blue striped bars) and women (pink open bars). * $p < 0.05$. ND= no diabetes, T2D= type 2 diabetes.

S16. Multilinear regressions investigating the impact of menopausal status vs sex hormones and metabolic parameters on counter-regulatory responses

	Hypoglycemic Clamp (n=27)		Hyperglycemic Clamp (n=27)		
	GH _{AUC} ^a	HF _{MEAN} ^b	GH _{AUC} ^a	HF _{MEAN} ^c	LF:HF _{MEAN} ^c
M1, Menopausal status					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.45*	-0.46*	-0.38*	-0.56**	0.47*
Model R^2	0.207 [†]	0.214 [†]	0.146 [†]	0.315 [†]	0.224 [†]
M2, Menopausal status and testosterone					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.51*	-0.45*			
Testosterone, std. β	-0.20	0.03			
Model R^2	0.246 [†]	0.215			
M3, Menopausal status and estradiol					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.39	-0.53			
Estradiol, std. β	0.11	-0.11			
Model R^2	0.214	0.221			
M4, Menopausal status and FSH					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.99*	-0.32			
FSH, std. β	0.59	-0.17			
Model R^2	0.268	0.220			
M5, Menopausal status and LH					
Menopausal status (ref. pre)	-0.39	-0.45			
LH, std. β	-0.08	-0.01			
Model R^2	0.209	0.214			
M6, Menopausal status and metabolic variables					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.36*	-0.34	-0.18	-0.42*	0.45
HOMA-IR, std. β	-0.37*	-0.36		-0.43*	
BFP, std. β			-0.61***		
fGlucose, std. β					0.05
Model R^2	0.338 ^{†§}	0.331 [†]	0.481 ^{†§}	0.479 ^{†§}	0.226
M6, Menopausal status and T2D status					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.39	-0.32	-0.23	-0.43*	0.34
T2D (ref. no T2D), std. β	-0.15	-0.39	-0.35	-0.33	0.34
Model R^2	0.226 [†]	0.350 ^{†§}	0.249 [†]	0.408 [†]	0.323 [†]
M7, Menopausal status and BMI					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.45*	-0.46*	-0.31	-0.54**	0.48*
BMI, std. β	-0.18	-0.27	-0.54**	-0.29	-0.10
Model R^2	0.239 [†]	0.287 [†]	0.437 ^{†§}	0.398 [†]	0.234
M8, Menopausal status and use of metformin					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.44*	-0.43*	-0.33	-0.52**	0.41*

	Hypoglycemic Clamp (n=27)		Hyperglycemic Clamp (n=27)		
	GH _{AUC} ^a	HF _{MEAN} ^b	GH _{AUC} ^a	HF _{MEAN} ^c	LF:HF _{MEAN} ^c
Metformin (ref. no), std. β	-0.05	-0.16	-0.21	-0.22	0.36
Model R^2	0.209	0.239	0.189	0.361 [†]	0.351 ^{†§}
M9, Menopausal status and use of antihypertensives					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.37	-0.33	-0.34	-0.42*	0.34
Antihypertensives (ref. no), std. β	-0.26	-0.37	-0.13	-0.42*	0.38
Model R^2	0.267 [†]	0.334 [†]	0.161	0.468 ^{†§}	0.354 ^{†§}
M10, Menopausal status and use of statins					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.36	-0.36	-0.35	-0.46*	0.32
Statins (ref. no), std. β	-0.24	-0.25	-0.10	-0.25	0.39
Model R^2	0.258 [†]	0.264	0.155	0.369 [†]	0.349 ^{†§}
M11, Menopausal status and tobacco use					
Menopausal status (ref. pre), std. β	-0.47**	NA ^d	-0.38	-0.55**	0.48*
Tobacco use (ref. no), std. β	-0.38*	NA ^d	-0.03	0.20	0.15
Model R^2	0.350 ^{†§}	NA ^d	0.147	0.354 [†]	0.248

* $p < 0.05$ for standardized beta coefficient (std. β), [†]model $p < 0.05$, [§] $p < 0.05$ vs univariate model, by likelihood ratio test. HF, power of the high frequency; LF: HF, ratio of the power of low frequency (LF) and HF; BFP, Body fat percentage; fGlucose, fasting glucose.

^alogtransformed prior to analysis. Measurements missing for ^b3 post- and 2 premenopausal women, ^c3 post- and 1 premenopausal woman. ^dHRV measures during the hypoglycemic clamp not available for any tobacco users.

S17. Correlations between sex hormones and counter-regulatory responses in men and women

Heat map where red indicate positive, blue indicate negative and white indicate neutral directions. Only significant correlations are labelled. HF, power of the high frequency of HRV; LF: HF, ratio between LF (power of the low frequency of HRV) and HF.

S18. Correlations between metabolic variables and neurohormonal responses in men and women

Heat map where red indicate positive, blue indicate negative and white indicate neutral directions. Only significant correlations are labelled. SBP, Systolic blood pressure; DBP, Diastolic blood pressure; HF, power of the high frequency of HRV; LF: HF, ratio between LF (power of the low frequency of HRV) and HF, WHR, Waist-Hip ratio.

S19. Linear regression models in men investigating the impact of sex hormones versus metabolic parameters on counter-regulatory responses to hypoglycemia

	ACTH _{AUC} ^a	GH _{ΔAUC}	GH _{ΔAUC}	HR _{ΔMEAN} ^b
Univariate models				
Testosterone	-0.41		0.30	
FSH		-0.47*		-0.49*
Model <i>R</i> ²	0.170	0.224 [†]	0.091	0.244 [†]
Bivariate models				
Testosterone	-0.13		0.15	
FSH		-0.41*		-0.43*
WHR	0.58**			
BMI		-0.33	-0.34	-0.56**
Model <i>R</i> ²	0.426 ^{†§}	0.325 [†]	0.183	0.552 ^{†§}

**p*<0.05 for standardized beta coefficient (std. β), [†]model *p*<0.05, [§]*p*<0.05 vs univariate model, by likelihood ratio test. ^alogtransformed and transformed to the square root prior to analysis, ^bmeasurements missing for 5 men.

S20. Linear regression models in women investigating the impact of sex hormones versus metabolic parameters on counter-regulatory responses to hypoglycemia

	GH _{AUC} ^a	GH _{AUC} ^a	HF _{MEAN} ^b
Univariate models			
LH, std. β	-0.40*		-0.37
Estradiol, std. β		0.35	
<i>R</i> ²	0.161 [†]	0.120	0.138
Multivariate models			
Estradiol, std. β		0.26	
LH, std. β	-0.37*		-0.10
HOMA-IR, std. β	-0.44*	-0.41*	
Age, std. β			-0.48
<i>R</i> ²	0.354 ^{†§}	0.283 ^{†§}	0.296 ^{†§}

**p*<0.05 for standardized beta coefficient (std. β), [†]model *p*<0.05, [§]*p*<0.05 vs univariate model, by likelihood ratio test. ^alogtransformed prior to analysis, ^bmeasurements missing for 5 women.

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